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THINK IT OVER! PRE-EMPLOYMENT SEARCH ON SOCIAL NETWORKING SITES¹

Abstract:

The rapid spreading of social networking sites such as Facebook, Twitter or WhatsApp has a profound impact on the workplace. Pre-employment search on these sites is common practice, yet it remains in the grey zone of law. This paper provides thoughts on the nature of these relatively new, digital channels of communication and examines the potential dangers of pre-employment screening from the angle of privacy protection and anti-discrimination. It examines how the right to privacy is balanced against the employers' lawful rights and interests such as to avoid vicarious liability and to recruit the best possible employees. Viewpoints from different backgrounds are discussed, highlighting the key patterns, legal lacunas and possible solutions.

Keywords: *social networking sites; privacy; employment*

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I. PLENTY OF INFORMATION ONLY A FEW CLICKS AWAY

It comes without surprise that a Google search is part of the recruitment process in many workplaces. It is a fast, easy, cost effective and overall, a very convenient way to find information about the job applicants. With a few clicks of the mouse the employer may not only check the candidates' background and verify some of the facts stated in the CV (professional experience, skills, qualifications etc.) but also acquires his first impressions of the future employee.² Given the wide spread use of social networking sites (SNSs), the Google search will probably lead to a profile such as Facebook or Twitter. Very often it is this stage where the important decision whether a candidate will evolve to employee is made. Profiles are tale-telling. Posts full of spelling mistakes speak volumes about the lack of written communication skills and most certainly ruin the effect of even the most impressive motivation letter. No matter how nice the recommendations attached to the application are, pictures suggesting drug abuse or extensive use of alcohol, or offensive comments about former company and colleagues will get the application shipwrecked. The employers most certainly look for red flags when they type the applicants name in the Google browser. However, the information they encounter (most cases without the authorisation or even previous knowledge of the owner of the profile) is more than warning signs. The posts, comments, pictures, even the music shared reveal a multitude of information on the lifestyle, political and spiritual views, family status or sexual orientation of the candidate. As we can see these data are not work related, on the contrary, they concern the candidate's personal life, often the most private aspects of it.

II. SOCIAL NETWORKING SITES³

Users of SNSs step outside their immediate family circle and enter the realm of virtual social interactions; they introduce themselves by sharing information; connect and communicate with other each other. SNSs are products of what the Spanish sociologist and cybernetic culture theoretician Manuel Castells calls "global network society", a society where the guiding principle is "being online".⁴ SNSs differ from physical places in many respects: they are mediated, and potentially global, searchable, and the interactions may

² S. D.Sanders, 'Privacy is Dead: The Birth of Social Media Background Checks', *S.U. L. REV.*, Vol. 39, Issue 1, 2012, p. 243.; V. R.,Brown, E. D.Vaughn, 'The Writing on the (Facebook) Wall: The Use of Social Networking Sites in Hiring Decisions', *Journal of Business and Psychology*, Vol. 26, Issue 2, 2011. p. 219.

³ Social networking sites are typical examples of the so-called Web 2.0 sites that enable users to interact with each other in a virtual community. The idea behind these sites is to connect people like friends; alumni etc. with one another on an informal basis and make communication more effective.

⁴ M. Castells, *The Rise of the Network Society: The Information Age: Economy, Society and Culture*, Vol. 1, Chichester, 2nd ed. Blackwell, 2010. p. 406.

be recorded or copied and also these sites may have invisible audiences or audiences not present at the time of the conversation.⁵ The popularity of these sites lies in their social functions. By giving users a forum in which they can create social identities, build relationships and accumulate social capital, Facebook and other SNSs fulfil basic human needs.⁶ This explains why in many cases employees and job candidates themselves contribute to the invasion of their privacy by oversharing.

Their placement on a “from private to public” spectrum proves to be difficult. In my opinion, because of their distinctive features, the objectives they serve and the environment they operate in SNSs have public, semi-public and private aspects at the same time. Images in academic literature attempting to capture posts with relevance to the employment relationship include “new water cooler” and “notice board of the staff canteen”. In the UK even if SNS profiles are set to private, there can generally be no expectation of privacy, the posts will be deemed to be public. In other countries the size of the intended audience plays a relevant role. However, even if SNSs posts are intended to be accessible to a limited audience, case law on “Facebook firings” from in and outside the European Union shows that privacy is of relative value. The semi-public aspect is also supported by the fact that these sites operate in a virtual space, thus whatever is put on the platform is relatively easy to search, reach, share and trace. The more limited the audience, the closer the information shared is to being considered private. One-to-one functions such as mail or chat should be treated as private and enjoy legal protection accordingly.

III. PRIVACY CONCERNS

Due to their inherent characteristics, SNSs pose a challenge to traditional privacy regulations, which are usually concerned with protection of citizens against unfair or non-proportional processing of personal data by the public administration, and businesses, and offer only very few rules governing the publication of personal data at the initiative of private individuals.⁷

Within the European context, the legal assessment of a pre-employment Google search is shaped by the principles of data protection enshrined in documents such as: Directive 95/46/EC⁸; the OECD Guidelines on the Protection of Privacy (hereinafter: OECD Guide-

⁵ D. Boyd and N. Ellison, ‘Social Network Sites: Definition, History, and Scholarship’, *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, Vol. 13, Issue 1, 2008., p. 210.

⁶ J. Grimmelman, ‘Saving Facebook’, *Iowa Law Review*, Vol. 94., p. 1206.

⁷ International Working Group on Data Protection in Telecommunications. p. 1.

⁸ Directive 95/46/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 October 1995 on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data OJ L 281 of 23.11.1995.

lines); the UN Guidelines⁹; the Council of Europe's Convention No. 108 (hereinafter: CoE Convention) as well as the national employment and data protection provisions. When it comes to the level of collective agreement, pre-employment data protection issues are seldom tackled.¹⁰ Below application of the following most important principles are examined: fair and lawful processing (as an overarching principle); data reduction and data economy; permission; purpose; direct collection; access; accuracy and limitation.

The overarching twin principle of fairness and lawfulness is the number one principle of the UN Guidelines, it is also enshrined in Art. 5(a) of the CoE Convention; in Art 6(1) (a) of Directive 95/46/EC. It is a crucial requirement, one that is embodied in numerous specific sub-requirements. It covers but it is not limited to existence of a fair and legal grounds. Art. 7 of Directive 95/46/EC lists six potential options; where personal data can be processed:

- a) based on the data subject's unambiguous consent or processing is necessary for:
- b) performance of a contract with the data subject;
- c) compliance with a legal obligation imposed on the controller;
- d) protection of the vital interests of the data subject;
- e) performance of a task carried out in the public interest; or
- l) legitimate interests pursued by the controller, subject to an additional balancing test against the data subject's rights and interests.

Naturally, irrespective of the existence of a legal ground, data processing must always comply with the principle of necessity, proportionality, purpose limitation and all the other general requirements discussed later in this paper. Out of the six grounds, those listed in (a), (b) and (f) appear to be reasonable candidates for justifying a pre-employment search on SNSs. Relying on Art. 7(a) is very shaky ground as the genuine nature of consent is always questionable due to the power imbalances of the parties. Though in itself it is – in my opinion – an insufficient justification, attaining consent complies with other data protection principles such as transparency. Art. 7(b) provides a legal ground in situations where “processing is necessary for the performance of a contract to which the data subject is party or in order to take steps at the request of the data subject prior to entering into a contract”. This article covers pre-contractual relations, provided that steps are taken at the request of the data subject, rather than at the initiative of the controller or any third party. However, detailed online background checks are unlikely be considered as necessary steps made at the request of the data subject.

⁹ Guidelines for the Regulation of Computerized Personal Data Files, as adopted by General Assembly resolution 45/95 of 14 December 1990.

¹⁰ G. L. Szóke (ed.), *Privacy in the Workplace: Data Protection Law and Self-regulation in Germany and Hungary*, HVG-ORAC, Budapest, 2012; I.Böröcz, 'A munkahelyi érdekek-összeütőközés rendhagyó formája: munkavállalók megfigyelése pró és kontra', *Infokommunikáció és Jog*, Vol. 10, Issue 55, 2013, pp. 99-101.

The employer may also try to rely on Art. 7(f). To select the best possible candidate is a legitimate interest. Careful selection is also important because the employer is liable for the damage caused by actions of employees committed within the scope or course of employment. To avoid vicarious liability and “negligent hiring” claims the future employer has to take reasonable action to examine the candidate’s background, to gain relevant information, verify documentations etc. However it has to be balanced against the candidate’s rights and interests (to express him- or herself freely, right to private life, etc.). It is also noteworthy that less intrusive measures are available to check the validity of the statements of the candidate. The employer may (with the consent of the candidate) ask for a reference about the former employee or search public databases (classified directory for example).

According to the principle of data reduction and data economy (also called as principle of necessity, non-excessiveness or proportionality by the various data protection instruments) data processing systems must be designed and selected to collect, process and use as little personal data as possible (see e.g. Art. 6(1)(c) and Art. 7 of Directive 95/46/EC, Art. 5(c) of the CoE Convention). This principle is infringed as Facebook reveals a multitude of mostly non-work related information.

The collection, processing and use of personal data are only admissible if either it is expressly permitted by legal provision or the data subject has expressly consented in advance. Generally no legal provision exists (except in relation to certain specific categories of workers) and the permission is also missing. In line with the principle of purpose, the purposes for which data is to be processed or used must be defined at the time of collection and personal data can only be processed and used in accordance with this purpose (See para 9 of the OECD Guidelines; Principle 3 of the UN Guidelines; Art. 5(b) of the CoE Convention and Art 6(1)(b) of Directive 95/46/EC). In our case the purpose is most likely the selection of the best possible candidate and verification of facts stated in the CV.

According to the principle of direct collection, personal data must be collected from the data subject, unless an exemption applies by law, or the collection from the data subject would require disproportionate effort and the justified interests of the data subject are not affected. Personal data in our case is not collected from the candidate, and as the collection from the data subject would not require disproportionate effort, the exception rule does not apply either, consequently this principle is violated.

Candidates have the right to know what information is collected about them, for what reason and how it will be used. The principle of access and openness is violated, because the data subject may not access the information that is stored concerning him or her after the Google search. The principle of accuracy (data quality and correctness) is enshrined in para 8 of the OECD Guidelines; Art. 5(d) of the CoE Convention and Art 6(1)(d) of Directive 95/46/EC. Assessing someone’s potential employability based on an online profile may produce false results. Profiles do not necessarily provide an accurate and up to

date picture of the individual. As it was demonstrated in the French test case cited above, pre-employment screens are often superficial and thus are very likely to lead to speculative conclusions. The principle of accuracy would require correction of incorrect personal data, however, as the candidate is unaware of the search let alone its result, he or she clearly cannot demand the employer to correct inappropriate data. Finally, the principle of limitation would require the employer to erase the personal data collected from the Internet once it is no longer necessary for the purpose for which it has been collected (i.e. the job is filled). This is generally unlikely to happen in practice.¹¹

IV. PRE-EMPLOYMENT GOOGLE SEARCH AS POTENTIAL DISCRIMINATION CASE

Google search does not only raise privacy concerns, it may also lead to discriminatory practice. According to EU regulations as well as national employment and data protection laws employers are only permitted to ask for personal information about the applicant's if the information is relevant to the specific job.¹² The main problem with Google search is that the employer also collects information that he or she would not have the right to obtain during a job interview. In addition this happens without the candidate's knowledge. Googling may very well lead to discrimination and unethical practices, applicants can be eliminated because the content they post online is considered to be inappropriate or it simply does not fit with the image of the company. A huge body of academic literature is dedicated to protection against discrimination including prohibition of discriminatory hiring (job advertisements and interviews infringing the principle of equal treatment etc.), the potential danger in a Google search from the perspective of discrimination is worthy of our attention as well.

To highlight the relevance of the issue I would like to speak of a recent field study conducted by academics of Université Paris Sud. During one year from March 2012 to March 2013 the researchers handed in more than 800 applications for real accountant job offers

¹¹ See for instance L. Pók, 'A közösség hálójában – Közösségi oldalak munkajogi vonatkozásai', *Infokommunikáció és Jog*, Vol. 48, Issue 1, 2012, pp. 10–17.; L. Horváth and A. Gelányi, 'Lájkolni vagy nem lájkolni? A közösségi oldalak használatának munkajogi kérdései', *Infokommunikáció és Jog*, Vol. 8, Issue 43, 2011, pp. 60–66; J. Németh, 'Az internet nem felejt – közösségi média-használatra alapított munkáltatói és munkavállalói felmondások', *Infokommunikáció és Jog*, Vol. 10, Issue 55, 2013, pp. 96–98. 96.; For an overview on Hungarian data protection law at the workplace see e.g. M. Arany Tóth, *A munkavállalók személyes adatainak védelme a magyar munkajogban*. Bába K. Szeged, 2008; J. Hajdú, *A munkavállalók személyiségi jogainak védelme. Az adatvédelem alapkérdései*. Szeged, Pólay Elemér Alapítvány, 2005; Jóri A. (ed.), *Adatvédelem és információszabadság a gyakorlatban*, Budapest, CompLex, 2010.

¹² J. J. Abrantes, 'Algumas notas sobre o direito do trabalhador à reserva da vida privada', in Amaral, F. et al (ed.), *Estudos Comemorativos dos 10 anos da Faculdade de Direito da Universidade Nova de Lisboa*, Vol. II, 2008., pp. 241–248.

in the greater Paris area. They adjusted the content of Facebook accounts of the candidates to manipulate the perceived origins of applicants (home town and language spoken). The twist of the experiment was that they only manipulated the Facebook profiles, not the application material, this way they could see the impact of pre-employment screening on the number of call-backs received from employers. The test applicant received a third fewer call-backs compared to the control applicant. During the course of the experiment they modified the profiles so that the language spoken by the applicants could only be reached by clicking on a tab. The results were surprising. In subsequent months, the gap between the two applicant types shrank and virtually disappeared suggesting that the future employers based their hiring decision on a search that only concerned the very surface of the profiles.¹³

The push toward the emergence of legal parameters to control the privacy aspects of SNSs in the employment context is a visible trend in the US. Lawyers warn of increasing numbers of “failure to hire” lawsuits if it can be proved that employers are using SNSs to gather information on the candidate’s protected characteristics (such as marital status, religion, race, sexual identity, political opinion or national origin) as a basis for hiring decisions.¹⁴ To give an example: In 2007 the University of Kentucky was looking for a founding director for the university’s astronomical observatory. C. Martin Gaskell applied for the position and being the best candidate by far, he stood a high chance of getting hired. Yet, at a certain point along the selection procedure the hiring committee found his blog, which discussed astronomy and the Bible from a creationist viewpoint. The same committee that had previously noted that Gaskell was “clearly the most experienced” candidate and had “already done everything [the hiring committee] could possibly want the observatory director to do,” recommended another candidate for the position. Gaskell sued for religious discrimination.¹⁵

V. POSSIBLE RESPONSES

The assessment of a pre-employment google search depends on the privacy awareness of the given country. In Finland the Data Protection Ombudsman explicitly stated

¹³ M. Manant, S. Pajak, N. Soulié, ‘Online Social Networks and Hiring: A Field Experiment on the French Labor Market’, *Social Science Research Network*, 2014., <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2458468>, (accessed: 12 December 2014.)

¹⁴ R. L. Waring and F. R. Buchanan, ‘Social Networking Web Sites: the Legal and Ethical Aspects of Pre-Employment Screening and Employee Surveillance’, *Journal of Human Resources Education*, Vol. 4, Issue 2, 2010. p. 19.

¹⁵ Gaskell v. Univ. of Kentucky, No. CIV.A. 09 -244-KSE, 2010 WL 4867630 (E.D. Ky. Nov. 23, 2010). in K. Carlson, ‘Social Media and the Workplace: How I Learned to Stop Worrying and Love Privacy Settings and the NLRB’, *Florida Law Review*, Vol. 66, Issue 1, 2014, p. 484. The case was later settled.

that employers cannot use Internet search engines such as Google to collect background information on job candidates.¹⁶ He said: “According to the Privacy in Working Life Act, employers can only view personal data provided by their employees, and this includes data about job applicants”. The response was a lot milder for instance in the UK. The Employment Practices Code published by the UK Information Commissioner’s Office simply advised employers to “[e]nsure there is a clear statement on the application form or surrounding documents, explaining what information will be sought and from whom” and “explain the nature of and sources from which information might be obtained about the applicant in addition to the information supplied directly by the applicant”¹⁷.

The above mentioned reactions came from expert bodies; however, we can also find hard law responses. A draft bill on “Arbeitnehmerdatenschutz” was produced on 25 August 2010 in Germany. The draft prohibited employers from using personal SNSs to screen applicants, but allowed the use of business-focused networks when conducting background checks.¹⁸ The Explanations by the Home Office on Internet searches of the employer highlighted that the employer may, in principle, gather information on an applicant from all publicly available sources (e.g. newspapers or Internet). Regarding online social networks, as far as they serve private use (e.g. Facebook, schülerVZ, StudiVZ or StayFriends), the employer may not use them to get information. Despite this, the employer may benefit from searching those SNSs that are intended to represent its members professionally (e.g. Xing, Linked In).¹⁹ Due to lack of consensus the draft was rejected in 2013.

VI. LESSONS TO BE LEARNED?

The arrival of social networking sites is perhaps one of the biggest changes in the workplace over the last decade. The spreading of these new channels of communication has both beneficial and adverse effects. They can combat inequality and accelerate human

¹⁶ W. McGeeveran, ‘Finnish Employers Cannot Google Applicants’, <http://blogs.law.harvard.edu/info/law/2006/11/15/finnish-employers-cannot-google-applicants/#more-187> (Accessed: 12 November 2015)

¹⁷ Information Commissioner’s Office, *Data Protection. The Employment Practices Code*, 2011, https://ico.org.uk/media/for-organisations/documents/1064/the_employment_practices_code.pdf, (accessed: 14 December 2015)

¹⁸ See § 32 Absatz 6 BDSG Access from, <http://www.arbeitnehmerdatenschutz.de/Gesetz/32-BDSG-Datenerhebung-vor-Beschäftigungsverhältnis.html>, (accessed: 14. December 2015)

¹⁹ <http://www.arbeitnehmerdatenschutz.de/Gesetz/32-BDSG-Datenerhebung-vor-Beschäftigungsverhältnis.html>, (Accessed: 14 June 2015); See also: P.Gola, ‘Von Personalakten- und Beschäftigtendaten’, *Recht der Datenverarbeitung*, Vol. 27, Issue 2, 2011; J. T. Lelley and F. Müller, ‘Ist § 32 Abs. 6 Satz 3 BDSG-E verfassungsmäßig?’, *Recht der Datenverarbeitung*, Vol. 27, Issue 2, 2011.

progress; the freedom of assembly and association, the right to strike²⁰ can be exercised not only traditionally but also on a virtual level on SNSs or other virtual platforms. It is undeniable that social networking sites provide a new forum for people (and workers) to communicate about different issues; they shape identity and create new cultures. However, because they make information relatively easy to access SNSs provide employers additional opportunities to monitor and inspect the job candidates conduct, on occasions even the most personal and sensitive aspects of it. The employers' need for information has to be balanced with the applicants' right to respect for their private life, freedom of expression as well as their right not to be discriminated. 'Workers don't leave behind their rights as persons (and certainly not their right to privacy and data protection)...'²¹ A clear-cut solution would be to avoid pre-employment Google search in general (see the Finnish example above). On a theoretical level, such a system can be backed up by referring to the very nature of SNSs: these sites operate without pre-edition, or any kind of previous control, therefore enable expression of very diverse and unfiltered opinions. The possibility of background checks have a destructive impact on the quality of online human interaction, in the long run they may force users to create duplicate profiles, and censor their online activities for fear of being judged by their future employer. Obviously, the acceptance of the current practice may have a chilling effect and render a widespread communication medium dangerous for people to use.²²

Yet, I think imposing a complete ban on pre-employment screens is not feasible mostly because the invisibility of the search and the benefits it offers (fast, cheap, and easy). The solution the UK Information Commissioner's Office advocates, that is to notify the candidates about the background checks and document which data is collected, is more realistic. A written policy that specifies what information or sites will be consulted before the decision is made, who will conduct the review, and what records will be maintained helps to prevent possible lawsuits. Before hitting "search" it is also advisable that the employer ask him- or herself if the search fulfils the general requirements of processing data or not. Is it reasonable? Are there other, less intrusive measures available?

To select the best possible candidate for the job is a legitimate interest of the employer; however Google search is not without its dangers. Although the current practice clearly goes against the most basic principles of lawful data processing it is unlikely to change also because of the users of the SNSs. While users do not intend their future employers to see their posts and pictures on Facebook or Twitter, it is them who make it possible for the public (including employers) to access information on their profile. The desire of

²⁰ The first virtual industrial action was organised by Italian employees of IBM on Second Life. See E. Kajtár, 'Bridge(s) over Troubled Water', *Pécsi Munkajogi Közlemények*, Vol. 4, Issue 1, 2011, pp. 117-131.

²¹ T. C. Moreira, The Digital To Be or Not To Be: Privacy of Employees and the Use of Online Social Networks in the Recruitment Process. *Journal of Law and Social Sciences (JLSS)*, 2, 2013, pp. 76-79.

²² L. A. Clark and S. J. Roberts, 'Employer's Use of Social Networking Sites: A Socially Irresponsible Practice', *Journal of Business Ethics*, Vol. 95, Issue 4, 2010, pp. 507-525.

self-expression, information sharing, networking, etc. is dominant when the profiles are shaped, the opposite desire, the one for clear separation of work and private life, the wish for solitude kicks in or is realised later (or too late). This is one of the reasons why pre-employment search on social networking sites remains in the grey zone of law.

For the time being candidates may protect themselves mainly by being cautious about what information they share online and by choosing their privacy settings wisely. This of course presupposes a certain awareness of one's digital footprint. As to the adverse effects, the biggest concern is the issue of how to provide evidence. Even though in discrimination cases the burden of proof is reversed, employment discrimination can often be difficult to prove. Though candidates are seldom in the position to present a *prima facie* case for discrimination, successful cases such as the one concerning the job at University of Kentucky cited above give rise for optimism.